

S=O, from sulphonamide group appeared at $\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the nmr spectral studies of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-ol in DMSO(D_6), the singlets at 2.28, 6.48 and 9.26 δ appeared due to CH_3 , pyrimidine ring C-H and O-H protons respectively. However, in case of 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)-pyrimidin-2-ol, two methyl groups attached to pyrimidine ring and benzene ring were characterised by two singlets at 2.15 δ and 2.25 δ respectively; the proton of the pyrimidine ring in this compound was observed at 6.72 δ . The aromatic protons were represented by two doublets centered at 7.2 δ (2H, *ortho* to methyl group) and 7.85 δ (2H, *ortho* to thiazole ring) while the O-H protons by a singlet at 9.2 δ . The absence of singlet at 6.48 δ and 6.72 δ in the coupled products of the two series of compounds confirmed that coupling had taken place.

Antibacterial properties: When screened at 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 4,6-dimethyl-5-(aryloxy)pyrimidin-2-ols exhibited activity of varying degree against all the three micro-organisms and the order of activity was $P. pyocyanea > S. aureus > E. coli$. On comparing the activities of the different compounds, it was observed that the introduction of methyl group in the arylazo group decreased the activity. However, the replacement of this methyl by an electron withdrawing group like halogen atom or a nitro group caused an enhancement in the activity, particularly against *P. pyocyanea*. Further, the exchange of methyl at position 6 by a tolyl group decreased the activity against *P. pyocyanea* while the activity against *E. coli* increased to a considerable extent, there being no marked effect on *S. aureus*.

Another important observation made in the course of this work was that replacement of the arylazo group by sulphonamido group rendered these compounds less active.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-Phenyl-3-methyl/phenyl-4-(*o/m/p*-substituted benzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones, 1-Phenyl-3-(*o/m/p*-substituted anilic)-5-pyrazolones and 3-Methyl/phenyl-4-(*o/m/p*-substituted benzeneazo)-5-isoxazolones as Possible Biological Agents

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EXTENSIVE work on the applications of 5-pyrazolones, isoxazolones and their derivatives in chemotherapy has been reported¹⁻⁵. Pyrazolones have also been used in analytical chemistry⁶. Keeping this in view some substituted benzene diazonium chlorides were coupled with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate and subsequent refluxing of the resulting products (I) with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively gave the pyrazolones (II) and isoxazolones (III). The reaction, in general, may be represented as follows:

Some anilic-5-pyrazolones were also synthesised by condensing malonanilic acids with phenylhydrazine. Purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were checked by tlc and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Melting points recorded are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Beckmann IR spectrophotometer. Malonanilic acids required for the work were synthesised by the method of Singhal and Ittyerah⁷.

Ethyl-4-bromo-2-methyl benzeneazo acetoacetate (I): 4-Bromo-2-methyl aniline (1.86 g) was diazotised in the usual manner. The filtered diazonium solution was run slowly into a well cooled mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (1.95 g) in ethanol (2.5 ml) and sodium acetate (10 g) in water (2.5 ml). A

yellow precipitate separated out immediately which was collected after 8 hr and recrystallised from ethanol. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$: 650 (C-Br), 1620 (-N=N), 2900 (C-CH₃), 1020 and 1095 cm⁻¹ (1, 2, 4 substitution in benzene ring).

Compounds 1-5 were obtained in the same way.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl benzene-azo)-5-pyrazolone (II): A mixture of 3.27 g of (I) dissolved in glacial acetic acid and phenylhydrazine (1.08 g) was refluxed for 1 hr. Orange-red crystals, obtained on cooling, were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$: 670 (C-Br), 1640 (C=O cyclic), 1542 (-N=N), 1250 (N-C₆H₅), 1460 and 1495 (five membered heterocyclic ring), 995 and 1040 cm⁻¹ (1, 2, 4 substitution in benzene ring).

Compounds 6-10 were obtained in the same way.

3-Methyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl benzeneazo)-5-isoxazolone (III): A mixture of 4.10 g of (I) dissolved in excess ethanol, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g) and sodium acetate (5 g) both dissolved in the minimum quantity of water was refluxed for 4 hr. Pale yellow crystals obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$: 605 (C-Br), 1720 (C=O cyclic); 1560 (-N=N), 1466 and 1560 (five membered heterocyclic ring), 960 and 1010 cm⁻¹ (1, 2, 4 substitution in benzene ring).

Compounds 11-16 were obtained in same way.

1-Phenyl-3-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl anilic)-5-pyrazolone: A mixture of 2.72 g of malon-4-bromo-2-methyl anilic acid dissolved in ethanol and phenylhydrazine (1.08 g) with 2 drops of conc. H₂SO₄ was refluxed for half an hour. White crystalline product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$: 610 (C-Br), 1665 (C=O cyclic), 1296 (N-C₆H₅), 2830 (C-CH₃), 3400 (-NH), 1402 and 1490 cm⁻¹ (five membered heterocyclic ring).

Compounds 17-19 were synthesised in the similar manner.

Biological activity: Some of the synthesised pyrazolones and isoxazolones were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity *in vitro*. The activity of a compound against the organism is indicated within the brackets.

Compound no. (6) against bacteria *E. coli* (+) and fungi *K. leb*; no. (7) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (1.56 r/ml); no. (8) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis*; no. (11) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (12.5 r/ml), *E. coli* and fungi *K. leb*; no. (12) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (3.12 r/ml) and the fungi *T. mentagrophytes* (25 r/ml), no. (13) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (12.5 r/ml); no. (17) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (12.5 r/ml), *E. coli* (++) and the fungi *C. albicans* and *K. leb* (++) ; no. (18) against bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (6.25 r/ml), and no (19) against the bacteria *M. tuberculosis* (12.5 r/ml), *E.*

coli (++) and the fungi *C. albicans* and *K. leb* (++) .

In addition to this, compounds no. (6), (11), (19) were screened for anti-inflammatory activity and no. (7), (9), (10), (14) and (18) for anti-convulsant activity, but none was found active except compound no. (19) which showed some anti-inflammatory activity.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compounds	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.	I	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	112	95.71
2	I	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	Br	72	89.90
3	I	CH ₃	Br	H	CH ₃	183	85.62
4	I	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	107	86.12
5.	I	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	CH ₃	88	77.68
6.	II	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	176	59.90
7	II	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	Br	135	35.04
8	II	CH ₃	Br	H	CH ₃	170	70.08
9.	II	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	153	51.73
10	II	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	CH ₃	205	49.65
11.	III	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	156	74.32
12.	III	CH ₃	H	OH	Br	180	55.74
13	III	CH ₃	Br	H	CH ₃	141	64.86
14.	III	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	119	50.55
15.	III	C ₆ H ₅	H	OH	Br	192	34.08
16.	III	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	CH ₃	126	41.94

All the compounds gave consistent carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
17.	OH ₃	H	Br	224	53.48
18.	H	CH ₃	Br	236	58.14
19.	Br	H	CH ₃	213	59.59

All the compounds gave consistent carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis.

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